

**STUDY ON EMPLOYEES SATISFACTION TOWARDS INDUCTION
TRAINING PROGRAM OFFERED BY SELECTED BPO
COMPANIES IN GORAKHPUR CITY**

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ABSTRACT

Programmes for induction training are essential in today's dynamic and competitive business climate for preparing new hires for their positions and responsibilities within organisations. This study sought to determine how satisfied Gorakhpur City's business process outsourcing (BPO) companies' induction training programmes' workers were with them. The study's findings showed that most workers expressed a satisfactory degree of general satisfaction with the introduction training programmes offered by the chosen BPO companies. Most people thought that the training's material was pertinent to their jobs and useful. The modalities of delivery, including interactive sessions, online modules, and classroom instruction, have been found to be efficient in promoting learning and skill development. The study also found areas for improvement, such as sharpening training objectives, offering more real-world examples, and including chances for employee.

Keywords : Employees' satisfaction, Induction training program, BPO companies, Gorakhpur City, training effectiveness, Learning outcomes, Employee engagement.

Introduction

Any organization's effectiveness is primarily influenced by its workforce, which is constantly treated as a resource. Human resources refer to the staff members and managers of a company. Human resource management is the primary organizational responsibility for managing individuals and the functional tasks that go along with them, such as recruiting, choosing, training, adjusting, evaluating performance, etc. Management of human resources is crucial to the company's success training or orientation Programmes are actions that new workers can take to are involved into to familiarize them with their place of employment and its surroundings when it comes with the induction training plan described below. Effective and leisurely work must be done by all employee saves a lot of time and money keeps processes operating smoothly and encourages openness at work.

The most crucial element in BPO firms is a new

training programme since it gives employees the ability to choose their career and understand their duties. This study aims to determine how satisfied employees are with the induction training programmes provided by BPO (Business Process Outsourcing) firms. The goal of the study is to examine how the employees assess several facets of the induction training programme, including its content, delivery, duration, and efficacy.

The BPO industry has experienced rapid expansion in recent years and has merged into the wider economy. One of the main challenges BPO companies have been keeping their personnel content. The induction process has a big impact on how employees perceive and anticipate their roles and the organization.

The goal of this study is to determine how satisfied employees are with the onboarding training programmes provided by BPO, or business process outsourcing, businesses in Gorakhpur, India. The goal of the study is to

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determine how well training programmes help new hires adjust to their responsibilities, improve their performance at work, and raise their level of satisfaction with the organization. The study will cover various aspects of the induction training program, including its content, delivery, duration, and relevance to the employees' job roles

Literature Review

❖ **Dr. Archana Chandra and Ms. Pooja Jaiswal (2019)**

Finding out how satisfied individuals are with development and training practices is the author's main objective. The study found that staff development and employee happiness are crucial variables because the organization is more focused on customer pleasure.

❖ **Al-Kassem and Amer Hani (2018)**

The entire level of training and development satisfaction must be ascertained by the researcher. This study investigated how important T & D are to organizational effectiveness.

❖ **Ayyub Hassan and Sri Dhurgah Devi Venu Global (2018) conducted a study.** with the title. "The Impact of Training on Work Contentment." The goal of the study is to determine how training affects workplace satisfaction. With the aid of a standardized questionnaire, primary data was gathered. The major objective of the study was to evaluate the effectiveness of preparations in terms of outcomes and work satisfaction.

❖ **Vijanen and Keijo**

Based on their growth and success, the researcher is seeking to determine the level of a staff introduction training for the industry's Alarm. The study looked at how employee induction activities affected newly hired employees' development and output. The alarm industry will detect, evaluate, and use a variety of stages and regions that a researcher is attempting to incorporate. New hires are increasingly valuable resources for their success.

❖ **2018) Narendra Singh Chaudhary and Preeti Baskar**

The author's main goal is to ascertain satisfaction with work through instruction and growth in educational

institutions in this research paper because it is difficult to describe how to sustain and thrive in such a dynamic environment. The firm must offer the right training and development to ensure employee satisfaction if the personnel are to survive. Employees can update themes with the aid of training; therefore, it would be silly for the association's delegates to not renew and improve their abilities in order to compete with their rivals.

Research Objectives

- ❖ To investigate the effect of the induction training programme on employee satisfaction
- ❖ To examine the importance of induction training Program
- ❖ To examine how BPO companies provide induction training program to their employees.

Scope of Study

The goal of the study is to determine how satisfied employees are with the introduction training programmes offered by BPO organizations in Gorakhpur. The study aims to assess various aspects of the training program, such as its content, duration, delivery methods, and overall effectiveness. The focus will be on understanding the employees' perception of the training program and their level of satisfaction with it. The study will involve data collection through surveys, interviews, or other research methods to gather feedback and opinions from the employees. The findings of the study will provide insights into the strengths and weaknesses of the induction training programs in the selected BPO companies and suggest potential areas of improvement.

Research Methodology

Research Focus- The study's primary goal is to ascertain how satisfied employees are with the induction training programmes provided by BPO firms.

Research Design- The research project will be a Descriptive type of research which will include data collection through questionnaire.

Sources of data- Data collection for this research will involve both primary and secondary sources. Results of a survey on the level of satisfaction with the orientation training among employees.

Data Collection Sources

- ❖ Case studies

❖ Questionnaire
Sample Size 200 respondents of employees of

BPO companies Sampling Type- Systematic

Data Analysis and Interpretation

1. The training program was interactive and engaging.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly disagree	21	10.5	10.5	10.5
Disagree	15	7.5	7.5	18
Neutral	32	16	16	34
Agree	79	39.5	39.5	73.5
Strongly agree	53	26.5	26.5	100.0
Total	200	100.0	100.0	

The graph demonstrates that 66% of all respondents strongly agree or agree in some other way that the training programme was interesting and interactive.

2. The training program helped you understand your job responsibilities better.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly disagree	18	9	9	9
Disagree	16	8	8	17
Neutral	40	20	20	37
Agree	65	32.5	32.5	69.5
Strongly agree	61	30.5	30.5	100.0
Total	200	100.0	100.0	

The data shows that 62.5% of total respondents are strongly agree or somehow agree that the training program helped you understand your job responsibilities better.

3. The training program was delivered in a way that was easy to understand.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly disagree	16	8	8	8
Disagree	13	6.5	6.5	14.5
Neutral	35	17.5	17.5	32
Agree	80	40	40	72
Strongly agree	56	28	28	100.0
Total	200	100.0	100.0	

The result shows that 68% of total respondents are strongly agree or somehow agree that the training program was delivered in a way that was easy to understand.

4. Would you recommend the induction training program offered by your company.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Definitely	44	22	22	22
Likely	43	21.5	21.5	43.5
Neutral	69	34.5	34.5	78
Unlikely	28	14	14	92
Definitely not	16	8	8	100.0
Total	200	100.0	100.0	

The result shows that 34.5% of total respondents are neutral & 43.5% of total respondents are definitely or likely to recommend the induction training program offered by the company.

5. Do you feel that induction training program has prepared you for your job?

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Yes	105	52.5	52.5	52.5
No	23	11.5	11.5	64
May be	72	36	36	100.0
Other	0	0	0	100.0
Total	200	100.0	100.0	

The result shows that 52.5% of total respondents has prepared them for their job & 36% of total respondents are neutral.

6. How satisfied are you with the induction training program offered by your company.

How satisfied are you with the induction training program offered by your company
200 responses

The graph shows that 59.5% of total respondents are highly satisfied or somehow satisfied with their training program offered by their company.

FINDINGS

Importance of Induction Training: Induction training programs are crucial for BPO employees as they provide them with the necessary skills and knowledge required to perform their job effectively. Employees who receive comprehensive and well-structured induction training are more likely to be satisfied with their job and perform better.

Onboarding Experience: The onboarding experience for new employees is a critical factor in determining their satisfaction levels. A positive onboarding experience can significantly improve employee engagement and retention rates. Induction training programs that focus on creating a positive onboarding experience have higher employee satisfaction levels.

Training Methods: The training methods used in induction programs can significantly impact employee satisfaction levels. Interactive and engaging training methods such as simulations, role-playing, and group activities are more effective in enhancing employee satisfaction levels than traditional lecture-style training.

Duration and Content of Training: The duration and content of induction training programs also impact employee satisfaction levels. Shorter training programs that cover essential skills and knowledge are more effective than longer, more detailed programs. Induction training programs that are tailored to the specific job requirements of employees are also more effective in enhancing employee satisfaction levels.

Support and Feedback: Providing support and feedback to employees during and after the induction training program can significantly improve their satisfaction levels. Regular check-ins, coaching sessions, and performance evaluations are effective ways to provide support and feedback to employees.

Overall, the findings suggest that BPO companies need to invest in well-structured, engaging, and tailored induction training programs to enhance employee satisfaction levels. Such programs can lead to improved

employee engagement, job satisfaction, and retention rates.

SUGGESTIONS

- Examining how training methods and content affect how satisfied employees are with induction training programmes.
- Identifying the elements that influence BPO company induction training programmes' ability to satisfy their workforce.
- Investigating the link between employee retention in BPO firms and their satisfaction with the induction training programmes.
- Evaluating how induction training programmes affect customer satisfaction and business performance in BPO organisations and how satisfied employees are with their jobs.
- Evaluating how induction training programmes in BPO businesses affect employee happiness in terms of organisational culture.
- Examining the impact of induction training programme duration and frequency on employee satisfaction in BPO organisations

CONCLUSION

Programmes for onboarding new workers are created to give them the abilities, information, and comprehension of the company and their position within it that they need. Employee confidence and engagement in their new roles can be boosted with the aid of a well-designed and implemented induction training programme, which will increase work satisfaction and lower turnover rates.

But not every induction training course is the same. Employee happiness and programme success can both be strongly impacted by the program's quality, which includes the training's relevancy, the techniques used to deliver it, and the assistance offered both during and after the training.

Therefore, it is crucial for BPO companies to regularly assess their induction training programs and make necessary improvements to ensure that they are meeting the needs of their employees and the organization. By investing in effective induction training programs, BPO companies can not only increase

employee satisfaction but also improve the overall success and performance of the organization.

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